

Generation of mmWave 5G signals using Microwave Photonics

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ABSTRACT

Bandwidth constraints is, nowadays, a mayor problem in the implementation of next generation 5G networks. In order to cope with increasing bandwidth demands, the use of the millimeter-wave (mmWave) spectrum, together with Radio over Fiber (RoF) technology has been proposed. In this work, we will present our recent advances in the generation of mmWave signals for 5G using Microwave Photonics.

Keywords: Microwave photonics, Radio over Fiber, mobile optical communications.

1. INTRODUCTION

We are in the Zettabyte Era. In 2016, the annual run rate for global IP traffic was 1.2 ZB per year and it is expected that annual global IP traffic will reach 3.3 ZB by 2021 [1]. Global IP traffic will increase nearly threefold from 2016 to 2021. Busy hour Internet traffic is growing more rapidly (51% growth) than average Internet traffic (32% growth) and the number of devices connected to IP networks will be more than three times the global population by 2021. Internet of the Things (IoT) [2] and 5G communications [3] are nowadays the most popular emerging scenarios to visualize the ever increasing need of bandwidth and cost per bit reduction but other still unimaginable applications/services will follow the demand for the same or higher growth rate of Internet traffic during the following decade.

In order to meet the requirements, the backbone network, the access network and data centres will require a further increase of bandwidth capacity. To avoid a 'capacity crunch', the researchers are striving to design network infrastructure that can carry more data and more efficiently than ever before. Optical networks, technologies and devices continue to play a key role for satisfying the human needs of higher demand of information at higher speeds and to reduce the energy footprint of Information and Communications Technology (ICT). The emissions due to ICT are estimated to reach by 2020, 1.27 gigatonnes of CO₂ (GtCO₂), that are divided into three categories: end user devices (53%), voice and data networks (24%) and data centres (23%) [4]. Globally, communication networks accounts for approximately 1.7 percent of total electricity consumption; data centres consume another 1.4 percent and there are concern about the degradation for communication networks in an energy constrained future [5]. Optical communications provide a unique medium of data transmission and photonic processing devices and techniques. Photonics in communications bring the best bit/energy ratio [6].

Concerning mobile communications, it is expected that the network will be based on small cells and the millimeter wave (mmWave) spectrum in the wireless access. However, to achieve the target bandwidth, these solutions require a reduction of the size of the cells (femto-cells) to get a better spectrum efficiency, leading to a drastic increase of the cost and makes it difficult the management of the network. Furthermore, scaling to the mmWave part of the microwave spectrum (~40GHz) permits to access a higher potential bandwidth, but the cost of transceivers increase, and mainly, the maintenance cost also increase. The optical links are going to be the solution for the 5G-fronthaul networks. Unfortunately, the bandwidth requirements cannot be cost-efficient by just using Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) techniques or complex modulation formats because a minimum of hundreds wavelengths may be required which is not scalable on chip. Spatial Division Multiplexing (SDM) together with Radio over Fiber (RoF) has been recently proposed as the best suited solution for implementing 5G fronthaul networks [7]. Indeed, the RoF solution is a promising solution to increase the capability of the network in terms of bandwidth and reducing link loss. RoF overcomes the problems associated to reducing cell sizes and scaling to the mmWave spectrum. RoF may enable to centralize all the data treatment on the Central Office, giving flexibility on the management of the network and reducing maintenance and deployment costs. Furthermore, the use of SDM is proposed as an additional multiplexing technique to further increase the bandwidth capabilities [8]-[9].

In this work, we demonstrate the optical transmission and generation of analog RF mobile signals in the mmWave band. The proposed system can be used for the transmission of 5G-NR waveforms.

Fig.1. Layout of the measurement setup.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup used for the mmWave RoF link is presented in Fig. 1. The generation of the mmWave optical signal is based on combination of double side band (DSB) and optical carrier suppressing (OCS) modulation techniques. The targeted RF frequency for transmission is 26.5GHz. In order to generate the RF signal, firstly, a laser was modulated by a 15GHz sinusoidal oscillator using an OCS approach. A Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) biased in the null point was employed to implement the OCS modulation. The theoretical output spectrum is sketched in Fig. 1, it consists of two tones separated 30GHz in frequency. After the modulator, an Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) is included to partly compensate for the modulator loss. The two tones are then fed to a second MZM biased in the quadrature point. An RF signal emulating the user data is used as modulating signal in the second MZM. We used the Rohde & Schwarz SMW200A as signal generator. The considered output constellation diagrams were 256QAM, 128QAM, 64QAM, 32QAM, 16QAM and QPSK, and the maximum symbol rate of the equipment was 500MSps. The RF output of the signal generator was centered in frequency at 3.5GHz. A second amplifier was employed to compensate the insertion loss of the modulator. Finally, the signals are injected in 10Km link of single mode fiber. Fig. 1 displays the spectrum of the transmitted signals, the information is DSB modulated on two carriers that are separated by 30 GHz. The 3.5 GHz RF-frequency has been chosen to alleviate the requirements of the filters.

After the 10Km link, the signal is detected using a single high-speed photodiode. The optical signal is then converted to mmWave domain. After the detector there is the presence of different beatings, the ones with the highest frequency are centered at 33.5GHz and another at 26.5GHz. In our experiment, we have focused on the detection of the signal centered at 26.5GHz. The contribution at 33.5GHz is filtered out in the RF domain. The received signal is then fed to the Rohde & Schwarz FSW43 signal analyzer, where the quality of the signal was measured using the Bit Error Rate (BER). The characteristics of the components used in the experimental setup are summarized in Table I. A TUNICS T100S-HP external cavity laser was used as an optical source, for MZM1 we used the MX-LN-40 LiNbO₃ intensity modulator of Photline. The Miteq phase-locked coaxial resonator oscillator BCO-10-15000-315P was used for the 15GHz sinusoidal tone. For the MZM2 a LiNbO₃ intensity modulator from JDS Uniphase was employed. Finally, the Finisar XPDV2320R dual band high-speed photodetector was used as receiver.

Parameter	Value
Laser power	10dBm
MZM1 insertion loss	4dB
MZM1 half-wave voltage	6V
MZM1 Bandwidth	30GHz
15GHz oscillator power	13dBm
EDFA1 gain	20dB
MZM2 insertion loss	5dB

Parameter	Value
MZM2 half-wave voltage	6.8V
MZM2 Bandwidth	15GHz
EDFA2 gain	20dB
Photodiode Responsivity	0.65A/W
Photodiode Bandwidth	50GHz
Photodiode optical return loss	27dB

Table.1. Parameters of the employed components.

3. MEASUREMENTS

First, it is important to evaluate the generation and the detection of the microwave photonics signals. These measurements are done without the 10km link fiber (i. e. back to back configuration). The link gain was estimated to be around -60dB. The output power of the signal generator was initially fixed to 7dBm, then for each modulation format the symbol rate was adjusted to get a BER performance of 10^{-3} , limit for forward error correction (FEC). Afterwards, for each modulation the output power was swept from 3dBm to 11dBm and the BER was recorded for each point. A summary of the results is shown in Fig. 2, where the BER as a function of the output RF Power is represented along with some examples of the received constellation diagrams. The maximum symbol rate achieved for 256QAM was 25MSps (200Mbps), 45MSps (315Mbps) in the case of 128QAM. In these two cases, due to the high density of the constellations the received constellation diagrams at high power (11dBm) clearly exhibit nonlinear distortion. In the case of 64QAM the maximum symbol rate was 150MSps (900Mbps), and 300MSps (1500Mbps) for 32QAM. The symbol rate limit of the equipment was reached for the 16QAM transmission (2000Mbps).

Fig. 2. BER performance of the system for 256QAM, 64QAM and 16QAM in back to back configuration.

However, after the transmission through the 10 Km single mode fiber the maximum symbol rates are reduced. A summary of the results is presented on Fig. 3, similar trends are observed as for the previous case but for a lower symbol rate. 16MSps transmission was obtained for 256QAM case (128Mbps). In the case of 128QAM a maximum symbol rate of 27MSps (189Mbps) was obtained. 45MSps was the maximum symbol rate for 64QAM (270Mbps). For 32QAM transmission up to 55MSps (275Mbps) was possible. 150MSps data transmission was possible for 16QAM (750Mbps). Finally, in the QPSK case the maximum symbol rate was limited by the equipment, reaching the 500MSps (1000Mbps).

Fig. 4. BER performance of the system for 256QAM, 64QAM and 16QAM after propagation through 10Km of single mode fiber.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Optical generation of RF mobile communication signals in the mmWave spectrum have been explored experimentally. We have arbitrarily generated signals in the K/Ka Band by photonic means to achieve a transmission throughput higher than 2 Gbs with off the shelf components.

We have implemented a 10 km link of single mode fiber to transmit the generated microwave signals. We have achieved a 1000Mbps data rate for a BER below 10^{-3} . Future work has to be deployed to face with the 5G network requirements.

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